

Circumcircle and incircle

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2015

Every triangle has a circumcircle and an incircle. We look at the following triangle:

For these triangles the sine law is valid: ($r =$ circumradius)

$$2r = \frac{c}{\sin \gamma} = \frac{b}{\sin \beta} = \frac{a}{\sin \alpha}$$

See Bartsch [1] chapter 6.4.1 p.224.

The cosine law:

$$c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cos \gamma$$

It follows:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{a^2 + b^2 - c^2}{2ab}$$

We know the relation $\sin^2 \gamma + \cos^2 \gamma = 1$. With $\sin \gamma = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \gamma}$ we obtain:

$$r = \frac{c}{2 \cdot \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{a^2 + b^2 - c^2}{2ab}\right)^2}} \quad (1)$$

Thus we know the circumradius r as function of the sides.

Now we express the inradius ϱ as function of the sides. We have (see Bartsch [1] chapter 6.4.1 p.224):

$$\tan \frac{\gamma}{2} = \frac{\varrho}{s-c} \quad s = \frac{a+b+c}{2}$$

Now we use the following trigonometric relations:

$$\tan \frac{\gamma}{2} = \frac{\sin \gamma}{1 + \cos \gamma} = \sqrt{\frac{1 - \cos^2 \gamma}{(1 + \cos \gamma)^2}}$$

With the third binomial formula we conclude:

$$\tan \frac{\gamma}{2} = \sqrt{\frac{1 - \cos \gamma}{1 + \cos \gamma}}$$

Now we solve the inradius:

$$\varrho = (s-c) \cdot \tan \frac{\gamma}{2} = \frac{a+b-c}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1 - \frac{a^2+b^2-c^2}{2ab}}{1 + \frac{a^2+b^2-c^2}{2ab}}} \quad (2)$$

We transform to:

$$\varrho = \frac{a+b-c}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{c^2 - (a-b)^2}{(a+b)^2 - c^2}} \quad (3)$$

From the equations for r and ϱ we can derive at $\gamma = 90^\circ$ special terms. It is valid $c^2 = a^2 + b^2$, with equation (1) we obtain:

$$r = \frac{c}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} \quad (4)$$

With equation (2) we get:

$$\varrho = \frac{a+b-c}{2} = \frac{a+b - \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}{2} \quad (5)$$

Vector representation:

Now it shall be $\vec{c}_B, \vec{b}_B, \vec{a}_B \in R^3$ position vectors that span the triangle (see figure):

The side vectors are calculated in the following way:

$$\vec{c} = \vec{b}_B - \vec{a}_B \quad \vec{b} = \vec{c}_B - \vec{a}_B \quad \vec{a} = \vec{c}_B - \vec{b}_B$$

Before we used the sine law in the following form:

$$r = \frac{c}{2 \sin \gamma} \quad \sin \gamma = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \gamma}$$

With the scalar product we get:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}}{a \cdot b}$$

$a := |\vec{a}|$ is the absolute value of a vector in R^3 . Composed it yields:

$$r = \frac{c}{2 \cdot \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}}{a \cdot b}\right)^2}}$$

Thus we have a representation of the circumradius in vector form. Now we turn again to the inradius ϱ . Before we had the equation:

$$\tan \frac{\gamma}{2} = \sqrt{\frac{1 - \cos \gamma}{1 + \cos \gamma}}$$

For the inradius we used the formula:

$$\varrho = (s - c) \cdot \tan \frac{\gamma}{2} = (s - c) \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1 - \cos \gamma}{1 + \cos \gamma}} \quad s = \frac{a + b + c}{2}$$

If we insert the scalar product again, then we obtain:

$$\varrho = \frac{a + b - c}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1 - \frac{\vec{a}\vec{b}}{ab}}{1 + \frac{\vec{a}\vec{b}}{ab}}}$$

We transform this to:

$$\varrho = \frac{a + b - c}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{ab - \vec{a}\vec{b}}{ab + \vec{a}\vec{b}}}$$

Thus we have a vector relation for the inradius, too.

Calculation of a right-angled triangle with circumradius and inradius:

We saw before that for the right-angled triangle the following equations are valid:

$$r = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$$

$$\varrho = \frac{a + b - \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}{2}$$

Added this yields:

$$2 \cdot (r + \varrho) = a + b$$

The other equation can be written as:

$$4r^2 = c^2 = a^2 + b^2$$

Now we define:

$$p = a + b \quad q = a^2 + b^2$$

We follow:

$$q = a^2 + (p - a)^2 = 2a^2 + p^2 - 2pa$$

We have a quadratic equation for a . We transform the equation to the normed form:

$$a^2 - pa = \frac{q - p^2}{2}$$

The known solution formula for quadratic equations used:

$$a = +\sqrt{\frac{q - p^2}{2} + \frac{p^2}{4}} + \frac{p}{2}$$

With $p = 2 \cdot (r + \varrho)$ and $q = 4r^2$ at last:

$$a = +\sqrt{\frac{4r^2 - 4 \cdot (r + \varrho)^2}{2} + (r + \varrho)^2} + r + \varrho$$

simplified:

$$a = +\sqrt{2r^2 - (r + \varrho)^2} + r + \varrho$$

and

$$b = 2 \cdot (r + \varrho) - a$$

Thus we have the both sides a and b as function of circumradius and inradius in the right-angled triangle. If a or b are known, then the construction of the right-angled triangle can be done with the Thales circle.

References

- [1] Hans-Jochen Bartsch "Taschenbuch mathematischer Formeln"
7.-9.edition 1986 VEB Fachbuchverlag Leipsic
- [2] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft &
Technik Verlag Berlin 2001